

REAL TIME ECG SIGNAL PROCESSING USING EFFECTIVE DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM FOR CLINICAL APPLICATION USING LABVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The principle goal of this work is to build up a compact and practical information securing (DAQ) framework for clinical applications.[1] This DAQ framework comprises of numerous modules, for example, control supply, isolators, Analog to Digital Converter (ADC), intensifiers, channels and interfacing circuits. The whole data obtaining circuit has been created exploitation this system in the principle intends to gather ECG signs of recurrence between 0.05 Hz and 113Hz. This recurrence information from the ECG flag is exceptionally useful in clinical applications like Sudden Cardiac Arrest (SCA) expectation cardiovascular infection (CVD) identification, and so on. ECG signals will be gathered from the question utilizing three leads framework and given to the DAQ for recording the ECG flag. The obtained motion through this DAQ would then be able to be exchanged to the LabVIEW through NI6008 information securing card. This DAQ interface is utilized to change over the info simple flag to yield advanced flag and to spare loads of ECG data inside the scratch pad utilizing LabVIEW programming. This procured motion from LabVIEW programming framework is utilized for advance clinical examination.

KEYWORDS: Data Acquisition (DAQ) System; ECG; LabVIEW.

INTRODUCTION

Electrocardiogram (ECG) in clinical analysis assumes indispensable part in deciding heart related maladies ahead of schedule before the circumstance turn out to be more regrettable like the different Heart sicknesses, for example, Cardio Vascular ailments (CVD), aspiratory infections, Sudden Cardiac Arrest (SCA) and so on. The ECG is produced from a nerve hub Sino Atrial hub (SA hub) which thus gives a jolt to the heart. The current is diffused on the divider surface of heart and manufactures a voltage drop crosswise over which is 1mV to 3mV inside a recurrence of 0.05 to 100 Hz. The goal of this venture work is procurement of constant ECG flag information, ECG flag sifting & handling, include extraction, & strategies, visual recognition of any variations from the norm in ECG by utilizing the most recognizable and multipurpose programming LabVIEW. The correct usage of LabVIEW graphical capacities lead us to work with ECG signals for handling continuously with extraordinary precision and accommodation.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

It is proposed to outline an Effective Data Acquisition System for Real time ECG signals handling utilizing LabVIEW. The ECG flag will be created utilizing ECG Simulator and gained utilizing 3 lead ECG information procurement circuit.

The three lead ECG cathodes will be put on the human body surface in light of Einthoven triangle. The terminal at RA (right arm) will be associated with the negative contribution of INA118 and cathode at

LA (left arm) will be associated with a positive contribution of INA118. The third anode will be put regarding the matter's correct leg (RL) and will be considered as shared conviction.

The yield of preamplifier (INA118) will be given to an Isolation enhancer for electrical wellbeing reason. This confinement enhancer will give electrical separation between the information and yield flag. The produced flag will be pre-opened up utilizing Instrumentation Amplifier (IA) and will be separated at a cut of recurrence of 0.05 Hz – 113 Hz. Since, ECG flag does not have any helpful data past 100 Hz.

This separated flag will be additionally enhanced. This opened up input further will be passed to the PC through NI6008 information obtaining card. This DAQ card has used to change over the simple ECG signals into computerized ECG signals at a determination of 12 bits. Besides, the GUI will be created more intuitive and easy to understand device to effectively gather the ECG information from the test system. The proposed equipment circuit will be easy to actualize and powerful to stifle the clamors created amid the information procurement. This framework will be had a capacity to record the ECG motion for ceaseless observing and stores the ECG information in .xls design interestingly with other existing frameworks.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig 1: Block Diagram of DAQ System

The block diagram of Data Acquisition System is shown in the figure 1. This system consists of 3 leads probes, Instrumentation Amplifier (IA), low pass filter, signal conditioning, NI DAQ, LabVIEW software. The DAQ systems consist of the ADC where the analog ECG signal will be converted into digital format.

- **3 LEAD PROBES :**

As the signal will be picked up as far as millivolts, it is vital that our anodes ought to have great contact with the skin and should be delicate and offers low protection. For our case, we look towards promptly accessible business items to accelerate our improvement. As the flag the cathodes will be grabbed in millivolts, the tests must be protected from the 50 Hz electrical noise and other commotion introduce noticeable all around.

- **INSTRUMENTATION AMPLIFIER :**

Since the basic idea of ECG is to monitor the potential difference between 2 points on the body, we will use an instrumentation amplifier (IA) for our purposes. The instrumentation amplifier offers low power consumption with higher accuracy and precision.

- **LOW PASS FILTER :**

The Low Pass filter will be used to retain the integrity of the shape of the signal. The design of the filter will be had maximally flat amplitude response.

- **SIGNAL CONDITIONING :**

The signal which will be obtained need to digitized it. So it will be ready to access on LabVIEW.

- **NI DAQ :**

NI DAQ will be used to convert Analog ECG signal into Digital signal. DAQ can be further used for recording of ECG data and connecting to computer for study of acquired ECG signal using LabVIEW.

- **LABVIEW :**

LabVIEW incorporates the making of UIs (named front boards) into the advancement cycle. The graphical approach likewise enables nonprogrammers to construct programs by relocating virtual portrayals of lab hardware with which they are natural. The LabVIEW programming condition, with the included illustrations and documentation, makes it easy to make little applications

DESIGN OF DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

The block diagram of DAQ system for design is shown in fig 2. Design of DAQ system includes amplifiers, High-pass filters, Low-pass filters, Isolation amplifier. ECG signals are used to convert heart activities into electrical potential which is of 1mV to 3 mV and for this minimum gain of 1000 is required for further processing. For this the DAQ system requires hardware which includes filters, amplifiers, and isolators. Two stages are there so two power supplies $\pm 12V$ and $\pm 15V$ required.

Fig 2: Block diagram of basic data acquisition system design

CONCLUSION

In this paper we see that LabView has great effect on signal processing. A compact and practical information securing (DAQ) framework for clinical applications is been made. The ECG signs of recurrence between 0.05 Hz and 113Hz through DAQ is able to be exchange to the LabVIEW through NI6008 information securing card. The motion from LabVIEW programming framework is used for advance clinical examination in most efficient and less complex ways.

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